

**Scientific exploitation of space Data for improved
Ionospheric SPECification**

DISPEC

Milestone 6:

**Report on Spectral analysis methodology and data
requirements**

Version 1.0

The DISPEC project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions programme under Grant agreement No 101135002

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Document Information

Milestone:	MS6 “Spectral analysis methodology and data requirements”
Date:	30/06/2024
Author(s):	University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn (UWM)
Work Package:	WP3 “Spectral analysis of data time series”
Work Package Leader:	University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn (UWM)
Type:	Technical/Internal Report

Abstract

The milestone presents the report on spectral analysis methodology and data requirements. The report comprises of mathematical foundations of short-term Fourier analysis, initial data requirements for three assumed data types and a rough demonstration of spectral analysis workflow.

Document History

Version	Date	Edited by	Reason for modification / Remarks
0.0	22/05/2024	W. Jarmolowski	Initial Draft
0.1	27/06/2024	W. Jarmolowski	Original Version
0.2	29/06/2024	Wojciech Jarmolowski, Paweł Wielgosz, Anna Krypiak-Gregorczyk	Revised Version
1.0	30/06/2024	DISPEC team	Initial Release

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Executive Summary

The DISPEC project offers new high-level data products based on advanced data processing techniques that improve data quality, provides estimates of ionospheric characteristics based on the joint processing of space and ground data, provides results from post-processing of data for improved ionospheric specification, and exploits long-term time series for the study of long-term trends in the ionosphere in connection to atmospheric long-term dynamics and geophysical phenomena [AD-1].

This document outlines data requirements and methodology of spectral analysis applicable to station-based, model-based and satellite-based ionospheric data. The DISPEC analysis will provide new high-level data applicable in correlation analyses, modeling and other Scientific Data Applications (SDA) tasks. The report includes a very preliminary round of processing with example data, demonstrating spectral analysis workflow. The parameters applied in this demonstration are unadjusted, and the figures have a preview character.

1. Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document presents the mathematical foundations, data requirements and algorithm demonstration of spectral analysis of the data to be processed in DISPEC project.

The document is divided into 6 sections:

Section 1 (the current section) describes the purpose of this document and its organization.

Section 2 lists the applicable and reference documents and contains the list of acronyms used in this document.

Section 3 presents spectral analysis methodology (mathematical foundations).

Section 4 presents initial data requirements.

Section 5 presents data processing domain and demonstration of applicable methods.

Section 6 is the summary.

2. Associated documents

2.1. *Applicable Documents*

The following table contains the list of applicable documents.

Table 1 “List of applicable documents”

AD	Document title
[AD-1]	DISPEC Grant Agreement: 101135002 – DISPEC – HORIZON-CL4-2023-SPACE-01
[AD-2]	Deliverable D1.1. Report on SoA and SDA Refinement

2.2. *Reference Documents*

The following table contains the list of references used in this document.

Table 2 “List of reference documents”

RD	Document title
[RD-1]	Dodson-Robinson S.E., Ramirez Delgado V., Harrell J. and Haley C.J. (2022) Magnitude-squared Coherence: A Powerful Tool for Disentangling Doppler Planet Discoveries from Stellar Activity. <i>The Astronomical Journal</i> 163(4): 169, DOI 10.3847/1538-3881/ac52ed
[RD-2]	Harris F.J. (1978) On the Use of Windows for Harmonic Analysis with the Discrete Fourier Transform. <i>Proceedings of the IEEE</i> . vol. 66. p. 66-67.
[RD-3]	Jin, Y., Kotova, D., Xiong, C., Brask, S. M., Clausen, L. B. N., Kervalishvili, G., Stolle C. and Miloch W. (2022) Ionospheric plasma Irregularities – IPIR – Data product based on data from the Swarm satellites. <i>Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics</i> , 127, e2021JA030183. https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JA030183
[RD-4]	Katsavrias, C., Preka-Papadema, P. & Moussas, X. (2012) Wavelet Analysis on SolarWind Parameters and Geomagnetic Indices, <i>Solar Physics</i> 280(2), 623–640. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11207-012-0078-6
[RD-5]	Manolakis D.G., Ingle V.K. (2011) <i>Applied Digital Signal Processing. Theory and Practice</i> . Cambridge University Press 2011, pp. 991.
[RD-6]	Stankovic L. (2015). <i>Digital Signal Processing with Selected Topics</i> . CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform, pp. 820.
[RD-7]	Tsichla, M., Gerontidou, M. & Mavromichalaki, H. (2019) Spectral Analysis of Solar and Geomagnetic Parameters in Relation to Cosmic-ray Intensity for the Time Period 1965 – 2018. <i>Solar Physics</i> 294(1), 15. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11207-019-1403-0
[RD-8]	Yamazaki Y., Matzka J., Stolle C., Kervalishvili G., Rauberg J., Bronkalla O., Morschhauser A., Bruinsma S., Shprits Y. Y., Jackson D. R.. (2022). Geomagnetic activity index Hpo. <i>Geophysical Research Letters</i> , 49(10), e2022GL098860. https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL098860

2.3. Acronyms

The following table contains the list of all acronyms used in this document.

Table 3 “List of acronyms”

Acronym	Definition
1D	1-Dimension
2D	2-Dimension
3D	3-Dimension

Acronym	Definition
4D	4-Dimension
BE	Eastern component of magnetic flux density
BGD	Borealis Global Designs EOOD
CSD	Cross-spectral density
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
DORIS	Doppler Orbitography and Radiopositioning Integrated by Satellite)
EIA	Equatorial ionization anomaly
EPB	Equatorial plasma bubbles
EPN	EUREF Permanent GNSS Network
ESA	European Space Agency
GIM	Global ionospheric map
GNSS	Global navigation satellite system
IGS	International GNSS Service
IPIR	Ionospheric plasma irregularities
ITRF	International Terrestrial Reference Frame
IUGG	International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics
LEO	Low-Earth orbit
LSTID	Large Scale TID
MSC	Magnitude squared coherence
MSTID	Medium Scale TID
Ne	Electron density
NOA	Ethniko Asteroskopeio Athinon – National Observatory of Athens
ONERA	Office National d'Etudes et de Recherches Aerospatiales
PCP	Polar cap patches
POD	Precise orbit determination
PSD	Power spectral density
RINEX	Receiver Independent Exchange Format

Acronym	Definition
STFT	Short-term Fourier transform
STEC	Slant total electron content
UPC	Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated
UWM	Uniwersytet Warmiński Mazurski w Olsztynie – University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn
VFM	Vector field magnetometer
VTEC	Vertical total electron content
TID	Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances
WP	Work-package

3. Spectral analysis methodology

This section presents fundamental formulas referring to Fourier-based spectral analysis of the signals. The term “signal” occurring within the scope of the report refers to the one-dimensional sequence of the data representing the quantity of interest, which has homogeneous interval of its recording in time and can be processed in spectral analysis. From other perspective, the signal in spectral analysis must have attained that processing level, which provide 1D series of single physical quantity stored in real numbers.

3.1. Discrete Fourier transform and power spectral density

The Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) is an approximation of the continuous Fourier transform. The continuous Fourier transform analyzes an infinite signal, which must be represented by the function or provide full frequency spectrum in some other way. When discrete real data are limited, i.e. defined only at discrete time intervals, the best approach is DFT. The forward and inverse DFT are given by ([Manolakis and Ingle, 2011](#)):

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_f &= \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n W_N^{-fn} & f &= 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \\
 x_n &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{f=0}^{N-1} X_f W_N^{fn} & n &= 1, 2, \dots, N-1,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

where the complex quantity W_N , known as the twiddle factor, is defined by: $W_N = e^{\frac{i2\pi}{N}}$. The vector x_n is a sequence of discretized time-domain signal to be transformed, f is harmonic number, n is the number of selected sample, and N is the number of all samples. The sampling interval is here $\Delta t = T/N$, for the spectrum at frequency $\omega_f = (2\pi) \frac{f}{T}$, and the transform has, therefore, a discrete limited frequency resolution $2\pi \frac{1}{T}$. The signal of time function $x(t)$ can be decomposed into frequency responses $X(\omega)$ sampled for the entire available ω spectrum. These responses can be also transformed back exactly to $x(t)$ by the inverse Fourier transform. The selected signal band can be subtracted from the data, which, contrary to simple methods of detrending, e.g.: moving average or polynomial, removes precisely this part of the signal, which we want to remove in terms of a frequency band. The discrete autocorrelation function of x_n is:

$$R_{xx} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n x_{n-l} \quad 2$$

The parameter l denotes shift between two analyzed samples in the units of n . The Fourier transform of the autocorrelation function for the sample x_n is defined as the power spectral density (PSD):

$$PSD_{xx,f} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} R_{xx} W_N^{-fn} \quad f = 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \quad 3$$

3.2. Short-term Fourier transform and evolutionary spectral density

The amplitude of signal responses in the frequency domain provides PSD at individual frequencies/wavelengths. The Short-term Fourier Transform (STFT) provides the calculation of time-variable PSD (Stankovic, 2015). It is typical that three frequency domain units can be applied in the terminology alternately, i.e. frequency, wavelength, as well as wave period. The evolutionary and windowed STFT is a modification of the DFT method, which computes the spectrum of overlapping segments of the time series. The data sequence to be transformed is multiplied by a window function which is nonzero for a short period of time (Harris, 1978; Stankovic, 2015). The STFT of the signal is computed as the window is sliding along the time axis, resulting in a two-dimensional representation of the signal. Mathematically, this is written as:

$$STFT_{x,f,t} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n w_{n-t} W_N^{-fn} \quad f = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$$

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where w_n is a discretized window function and t is its time index. STFT of a data sequence x_n describes its local spectral content near the moment t as a function of f . Moving the center of the window w_{n-t} along the time axis allows for obtaining snapshots

of time-frequency behavior of x_n . STFT is used in the calculation of PSD for each sample. These PSDs form then 2D spectrogram shape, which depends on the window size and overlay size of the windows. This corresponds to the computation of the STFT squared magnitude of the signal sequence x_n :

$$S_{xx,f,t} = |STFT_{x,f,t}|^2$$

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The size and shape of the analysis window can be modified depending on the purpose. A shorter window will produce more accurate results in timing at the expense of precision in frequency. A longer window will provide a more precise frequency representation at the expense of precision in time location. The windowing of STFT can be performed e.g. with the use of Tukey window. Tukey window, also known as the cosine-tapered window, can be regarded as a cosine lobe of width $\frac{r}{2}(N-1)$ that is convolved with a rectangular window of width $(1 - \frac{r}{2})(N-1)$. The equations defining Tukey window are:

$$w_{TU}(n) = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \cos \left(\frac{2\pi}{r} \frac{n-1}{N-1} - \pi \right) \right] & , \quad n < \frac{r}{2}(N-1) + 1 \\ 1 & , \quad \frac{r}{2}(N-1) + 1 \leq n \leq N - \frac{r}{2}(N-1) \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \cos \left(\frac{2\pi}{r} - \frac{2\pi}{r} \frac{n-1}{N-1} - \pi \right) \right] & , \quad N - \frac{r}{2}(N-1) < n \end{array} \right\}$$

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where r is the ratio between 0 and 1. The Tukey window main parameter r can be set to arbitrary value between 0 and 1, which changes level of edge effects elimination. The use of longer or shorter window is always a question of compromise, as the length of the window provides increase of frequency resolution at the costs of time resolution.

3.3. Cross-spectral density

The PSD represents the distribution of a signal over the frequency spectrum. The cross-spectral density (CSD) provides the information about resonant frequencies for a pair of signals. The CSD is a type of correlation measure that determines dependencies between the signals in specific bandwidths. In the bandlimited system, two data series may exhibit strong dependence in one frequency range, having no dependence in another one. Simply speaking, the CSD can be used to find mutual resonant frequencies in a pair of signals. The cross-correlation function of x_n and y_n is then:

$$R_{xy} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n y_{n-l}$$

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The parameter l denotes shift between two samples of two analyzed sequences in the units of n . Mathematically, CSD is defined using a Fourier transform of cross-correlation function between the two signals. For discretely sampled signals in the time domain, the DFT algorithm is used to determine the CSD:

$$CSD_{xy,f} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} R_{xy} W_N^{-fn} \quad f = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1 \quad 8$$

The CSD with a spike at some frequency indicates that the pair of signals x_n and y_n is periodically correlated and this is a resonant frequency. If the CSD is nearly flat, then the pair of signals is uncorrelated.

The CSD is a function of frequency that can change over time. The data sequences can be therefore divided into analysis windows of equal length, which can overlap. The STFT is applied to each window, and DFT operation is applied to the convolution of two signals. These evolutionary CSD estimates form then 2D cross-spectrogram based on the signal sequences of the same length x_n and y_n :

$$S_{xy,f,t} = STFT_{x,f,t} (STFT_{y,f,t})^* \quad 9$$

where $*$ denotes complex conjugate.

3.4. Magnitude Squared Coherence

The CSD is a relative measure of cross-covariance. The related statistical quantity describing correlation of two time series is called coherence. A frequent form of coherence based on CSD estimates is sometimes called magnitude-squared coherence (MSC). The MSC function estimates a normalized extent to which a signal x_n is correlated with signal y_n . The MSC function reads:

$$MSC_{xy,f} = \frac{|CSD_{xy,f}|^2}{PSD_{xx,f} PSD_{yy,f}} \quad 10$$

The cross-spectra in the numerator ranges from 0 to the product of the two auto-spectra in the denominator. In other words, the MSC is a normalization of the CSD by the product of the two PSDs, providing the correlation measures. The normalization of the coherence compensates for large values in the cross spectrum that result solely from large power. If x_n and y_n are identical signals, then their PSDs are equal to each other and to the CSD. In this case, the coherence is 1 at all frequencies. If x_n and y_n describe completely independent processes, then the CSD is 0 for all frequencies and so is the coherence. Between these two extremes the possible relationships between two signals can be measured by MSC function.

In case when the magnitude-squared coherence is calculated based only on a single estimate of each of $PSD_{xx,f}$, $PSD_{yy,f}$, and $CSD_{xy,f}$, the result is $MSC_{xy,f} = 1$

(Dodson-Robinson et al. 2022). Therefore, we have to divide time series into multiple segments, and then meaningful coherence estimate comes from averaging multiple estimates of the numerator and denominator in Eq. (10). The procedure reads:

$$MSC_{xy,f,t} = \frac{|\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} CSD_{xy,f}^k|^2}{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} PSD_{xx,f}^k \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} PSD_{yy,f}^k} \quad 11$$

The accuracy of MSC strongly depends on the number of independent segments due to its' statistical nature. Therefore its accuracy at low frequencies can suffer in case of limited time series length.

4. Data requirements

The satellite along-track data are referred to time-space-frequency domain in spectral analysis, whereas ground-based series will be considered in time-frequency domain. This fact and different spatial reference of data collection (and possibly other factors) slightly differentiate their data requirements, but they are generally similar. The requirements between station-based data and model-based data are even more compatible. The main points referring to data arrangement are listed in separate bullets for satellite and station-based, whereas model-based have listed only significant differences in respect of station-based (ground-based) data.

4.1. Satellite along-track data

The LEO satellite signals are time-space data collected during fast run of the satellite along the orbit. An example LEO speed for Swarm satellite is around 7.6 km/s, which makes 1D in-situ Ne signal or topside STEC from POD receivers really transient measurements of ionospheric variations during very short time spans. The scale of ionospheric variations over such short time intervals is not large, so LEOs detect mainly spatial characteristics of ionospheric variations. However, different variations can have different spatiotemporal scales, which can be recognized better with spectral analysis. It can be assumed that different type of observations are affected by different number of factors, and they theoretically can affect the signal at different frequencies, which can depends e.g., on the distance from the source. Aside from that, it must be pointed that in-situ observations are theoretically under an influence of smaller number of factors than e.g. STEC data from precise orbit determination (POD) GNSS receivers. This is because in-situ observed Ne refers to only one altitude, whereas POD STEC is an integral over a broad part of ionosphere, and more processes can disturb this wider altitude span.

The complexity of along-track satellite data suggests that high-level products from spectral analysis can better represent different variations of ionospheric parameters triggered by different sources, e.g. processes generated by the Sun, magnetosphere and

other coupled environments. Generally speaking, the band-pass filtering of along track data should provide an opportunity for global reconnaissance of ionospheric irregularities of different origin. There are at the moment no global models of irregularities considering specific kind or origin, nor combined models grouping irregularities of various size and origin. The Swarm Ionospheric Plasma Irregularities (IPIR) product ([Jin et al. 2022](#)) collects irregularities determined by gradient approach and provides flags determining Equatorial Plasma Bubbles (EPB) and Polar Cap Patches (PCP) along the Swarm data records. The IPIR constitutes an important base for the reference. However, the application of STFT facilitates a more precise analysis of continuous frequency range, and therefore an advantage is expected from high-level products based on band-pass filtering. The following data requirements are important in DISPEC spectral analysis:

- The first requirement of spectral analysis is homogeneous data spacing over time (sampling frequency)
- The optimal data level is as close to observational as possible, i.e. including only processes necessary for creation of data time-space series of analyzed quantity. Any denoising, filtering, averaging or smoothing processes destroy data spectrum. The closer the data to original observations, the better for the analysis. It is better to preserve the noise, than to smooth or average the data.
- One of most desired data properties in respect of spectral analysis is possibly highest continuity and the lowest number of data gaps. Regarding data gaps, in general, the gap size determines the lowest frequency, down to which evolutionary PSD cannot be determined in time of gap occurrence, starting from the Nyquist frequency. The along-track data differ in this regard, also due to their acquisition method. For instance, Ne measured in situ with 2Hz resolution is besides technical issues continuous along the trajectory, whereas POD STEC records are based on the GNSS-LEO links, which are missed after several hours. The along-track continuity over entire orbital revolution can be only acquired from averaged solutions, which must lose some high signal frequencies after averaging.
- The frequency of data collection approximately determines Nyquist frequency. The length of continuous data span or the lowest spherical harmonic significant in global modeling of measured quantity determines the lowest frequency of STFT analysis.
- The time resolution of primary analyzed data and ancillary data must be the same in cross-spectral analysis or must be sampled at the same interval. Suggested method is resampling of the higher frequency at lower frequency, with no averaging. If some interpolation is necessary, the simplest methods are recommended (e.g. nearest neighbor, linear etc.), as they generate a minimal artificial signal.

- The frequency bands of high-level products are dependent on the analyzed signal structure, which will be an object of investigation in DISPEC.
- The availability of data noise estimates is useful if we need absolute estimation of spectral analysis accuracy, otherwise, only a relative estimation of accuracy or statistical significance can be done.
- In case of time-space-frequency analysis, recalculation of frequency to wave period, and to wavelength can be done. The wavelength will represent spatial scales of analyzed ionospheric structures.

4.2. Ground-based time-series of data

The ground-based stations built for different type of observations (GNSS, Digisondes, DORIS etc.) collect time series of data at fixed geolocations. However, the networks of such stations provide the same type of observations at different locations on the Earth, which gives more advantage, as different locations can be specific in respect of ionospheric activity. The ionospheric conditions over such stations vary over time, as it is influenced by different internal (Earth-fixed) and external processes. These processes occur in the lithosphere, ionosphere, magnetosphere or on the Sun. Several processes are periodic at some already well-known wave periods, which is confirmed in the research studies ([Tsichla et al. 2019](#), [Katsavrias et al. 2012](#)). The same and other processes exhibit also minor wave-like variations at different frequencies. By collecting a long-time (the decades) series of ground-based data recorded at very dense time interval (e.g. minutes, seconds), we become able to analyze a really wide frequency band of ionospheric variations from months down to minutes. Some of these variations exhibit a longer persistence in terms of repeated full wave periods, which can be assessed as periodicity. The other shorter wave-like signals can be transient variations, but can be also important and correlated with external drivers. The Sun rotates in a certain period, while the Earth rotates in another period, and orbits the Sun in yet another period. There are even more periodic processes in Sun-Earth environment, and even more reasons for analysis of periodicity and periodic variations in the ionosphere. The high-level products based on band-pass filtering are a chance for representation of selected ionospheric variation e.g. characteristic for selected processes. The other important issue is an elimination of unwanted masking signals like diurnal or seasonal. Despite different applicability of stationary ground-based data in comparison to along-track data, data requirements for station-based data are similar in DISPEC spectral analysis:

- The first requirement of spectral analysis is homogeneous data spacing over time (sampling frequency)
- The optimal data have numerical resolution of the data corresponding to their spectral content. i.e. consecutive data values preserve spectral signal details at

Nyquist frequency. The closer the data to original observations, the better for the analysis. It is better to preserve the noise, than to smooth or average the data.

- The highest continuity and the lowest number of data gaps are desired properties. The gap size determines the lowest frequency, down to which evolutionary PSD cannot be determined in time of gap occurrence, starting from the Nyquist frequency. Therefore, short gaps do not affect analysis at lower frequencies.
- The frequency of data collection approximately determines Nyquist frequency, whereas the length of continuous data span determines the lowest frequency of STFT analysis.
- The time resolution of primary analyzed data and ancillary data must be the same in cross-spectral analysis or must be sampled at the same interval. Suggested method is resampling of the higher frequency at lower frequency, with no averaging. If some interpolation is necessary, the simplest methods are recommended (e.g. nearest neighbor, linear etc.), as they generate a minimal artificial signal.
- The frequency bands of high-level products are dependent on the analyzed signal structure (to be investigated in DISPEC).
- The availability of data noise estimates is useful if we need absolute estimation of spectral analysis accuracy, otherwise, only a relative estimation of accuracy or statistical significance can be done.
- In case of time-frequency analysis, recalculation of frequency to wave period is only applicable. The wave period will correspond to the period of variation.

4.2 Model-based time-series of data

Global ionospheric maps (GIMs) are an example of ionospheric model, where global grids of ionospheric VTEC are stored as 2D maps having a third dimension, which is time. These maps represent averaged states of global ionospheric VTEC for selected time intervals, which are typically 1h. However, both denser GIMs with time interval 15 minutes and sparser ones with 2h resolution are available. The GIMs can be sampled horizontally in space, and in time. The assumed type of generated data series in DISPEC are time-series, which refer to single interpolated geolocations. This makes domain of these series being the same as for ground-based time series collected at the ground stations. On the other hand, the stations are typically a source of data for models like GIM (which is based primarily on IGS GNSS stations). The difference between station-based time series and model-based time series arises at higher frequencies. The signal from the stations has original sampling rate, which is smoothed/distorted in the models, due to their limited

space/time resolution (typical spatial resolution of GIM is 5° in latitude and 2.5° in longitude) and modeling techniques. The other type of models can be tomographic models, which have more than one altitude layer of grids, and therefore third spatial dimension is additionally available. The third dimension gives an opportunity for sampling from 3D space, but the dimension over which the spectral analysis can be performed is still the time, as this is the only dimension rich in frequencies necessary to built multi-frequential domain. Therefore requirements referring to model-based data are generally very similar to those for station-based series, with few exceptions:

- The investigation how the resolution of the data corresponds to their spectral content has no practical importance, as we cannot increase spectral content. The models will often provide smoother series in comparison to numerical resolution, or occasionally can have more spectral content with respect to Nyquist frequency. The lower frequency out of two (sampling or spectral content) will determine analyzed high frequencies in STFT.
- As the model is a higher-level product, unavailability of accuracy estimates will give even more relativeness of spectral analysis accuracy estimates.

5. Data processing domain and applicable methods

The idea of generation of high-level products from original data is stimulated by the fact of complexity of data time series and data time-space series, which makes data complicated in the analyses of physical processes. The concept of high-level product is based on the application of spectral analysis and band-pass filtering preserving narrower signal bands, which are more useful in the applications, like modeling, process analysis or correlation analysis. The physical domain of spectral data analysis is frequency domain, which is sampled from time domain in case of stationary (typically ground-based) data or from time-space domain typical for satellite moving platforms. The idea of spectral processing includes five primary steps, which are similar for satellite and ground-based data, aside from different units of workspace:

- High-pass filtering (detrending) – necessary to have a clear spectrogram free of low-frequencies and so-called „zero term”, which in many signals have the largest amplitudes impeding the analysis
- Time-space-frequency or time-frequency analysis (evolutionary PSD) and spectrograms of primary and ancillary data
- Cross-spectral analysis of primary and ancillary data (evolutionary CSD)
- Coherence analysis (MSC) and its relative accuracy estimate
- Generation of high-level datasets by band-pass filtering

5.1 Satellite data domain

The low-Earth orbit (LEO) satellite data are referenced to space and time, and LEO position changes with respect to both domains. Therefore satellite data are time-space series, and spectral characteristics can be considered in three linked units: frequency, wave period, as well as in wavelength. The evolutionary PSD analysis of LEO satellite data will be time-space-frequency STFT analysis.

5.1.1 Spectral analysis

The fast LEO movement makes the along-track signals more spatially referenced than referenced to a time unit, although the time is a variable of their primary reference in the files. The consecutive repeated orbital tracks at close geolocations observe more temporal changes, in comparison to single satellite pass. In single pass, the spatial location change provides more signal variations than time lapse. Generally, the geophysical signals in space have different spectral characteristics in terms of PSD distribution over frequency axis, and different frequencies can be dominating in their global PSD. However, in large amount of cases the lowest frequencies provide the highest PSD, and the lowest one is often called “zero degree term”. The example Ne from Swarm in situ survey belongs to this group. Therefore, the lowest frequencies of the signal substantially dominate and impede observation of higher frequencies if we calculate PSD for entire unfiltered signal without application of an exponential scale. The exponential scale of PSD masks the relation between the signal content at different frequencies, which is disadvantageous in some applications. This fact brings some risk also for DISPEC analyses based on wide variety of data, and therefore high-pass filtering is used as the method for signal detrending. The low-frequency signal can be removed starting from selected wave period with the application of some transition band, where PSD is smoothed in order to avoid generation of wave-like residuals at the filtering bound. The example high-pass filtering procedure for in situ Swarm Ne signal is shown in Fig. 1. The trend is generated by low-pass filter, then original signal minus trend provide the residuals, which become high-pass filtered signal. These residuals are shown in bottom subfigure of Fig. 1.

Figure 1 Swarm Alpha in-situ Ne (black line) along one selected orbital arc and trend (red line) determined by DFT with maximum wave period of 30 sec (upper figure). Residual Ne after subtraction of 30 sec trend (bottom figure). Red dashed lines denote pass of equator, blue dashed – closest approach to poles.

The high-pass filtering performed in fact by the subtraction of low-pass trend provides the signal within a limited frequency band, which has more homogeneous PSD, i.e. the amplitudes are more homogeneous. This facilitates evolutionary spectral analysis, which can be treated as time-space-frequency analysis, due to abovementioned LEO signal properties. The evolutionary spectral analysis is performed by STFT method with the application of selected time window (e.g. Tukey window). The size and shape parameters of the window must be selected. The manipulation of window size and type can significantly modify evolutionary PSD shape, and therefore several iterations must be often performed before the selection of window parameters, overlap parameters and time/frequency resolution of the analysis. All these parameters are selected empirically with the focus on desired resolution of the spectrogram in both time and frequency directions, which provide possibly the clearest view on the spectral characteristics. The example spectrogram of residual Ne along one orbital circle of Swarm A is shown in Fig. 2. This spectrogram has applied a 120 sec. Tukey window facilitating a preview of signal characteristics with a reasonable resolution in frequency, and valuable resolution over time/space axis. A shorter window in STFT would reveal a more precise time/space location of Ne disturbances, but this would be inherently associated with even worse frequency resolution. It should be pointed that heterogeneity of PSD of fast collected satellite signals comes mostly from the spatial diversity of ionospheric Ne. Due to fast spacecraft movement, temporal variations of the ionosphere can only weakly affect the signal and the disturbances typically are characteristic to selected latitudes and longitudes.

Figure 2 Swarm Alpha orbital footprint with night/day terminators at the start/end of the selected orbital track (upper). Swarm residual Ne spectrogram with indicated equator (red dashed) and pole (blue dashed) passes (bottom).

In case of the along-track satellite signals, the ideal sources of ancillary signals can be the observations of another physical quantities collected by independent payload on the same spacecraft. The examples useful for Swarm Ne analyses can be for instance the magnetic field components from vector field magnetometer (VFM). The magnetic field is coupled with electric field, which makes interesting a common assessment of magnetic field data and Ne data. The electric and magnetic fields are both measured in situ, which gives them a common spatiotemporal reference. The example selected quantity coupled with Ne can be the magnetic BE component, which can be high-pass filtered in exactly the same way as Ne. The result of this filtering is shown in Fig. 3. The VFM data taken for current comparison has temporal resolution of 1 Hz, which is only twice lower than Ne

resolution. The spectrogram of residual BE component is given in Fig. 4, which presents significant variations of BE signal solely in auroral regions.

Figure 3 Swarm Alpha in-situ BE component (black line almost hidden behind the trend) along one selected orbital arc and trend (red line) determined by DFT with maximum wave period of 30 sec (upper figure). Residual BE after subtraction of 30 sec trend (bottom figure). Red dashed lines denote pass of equator, blue dashed – closest approach to poles.

Figure 4 Swarm Alpha residual BE spectrogram with indicated equator (red dashed) and pole (blue dashed) passes.

pointed out that values at this preliminary stage can be far from final in the project, and are used only to illustrate technical nature of MSC calculation.

Figure 6 Example test of coherence approximation for residual Ne and BE from Swarm Alpha with indicated equator (red dashed) and pole (blue dashed) passes. The coherence values are here of preliminary nature and need parameter adjustment and accuracy assessment (have no bigger statistical meaning at the moment, due to the work needed for their adjustment).

5.1.2 High-level outputs

The concept of high-level products generated from spectral analysis is based on band-pass data filtering and an assumption that division of complex signals brings obvious benefits for data analysis. There are several problems with data, and there are many attempts to solve them by intermediate measures. The examples are: detrending with the use of deterministic functions like polynomials, extracting of high-frequency variations with the use of gradients, or de-noising with the application of moving average. The removal of some middle frequency band (e.g. variation at some characteristic wave period like diurnal or annual) is even impossible without precise spectral analysis. Therefore, selection of some narrow band from the complex signal can remove unwanted properties like long-term trend, noise observed at some characteristic frequency or dominating signal from middle frequency. The detrending bounds can reach high frequencies, which is impossible to attain with polynomials. The band-pass filtered signals from different frequency bands can be sensitive to separate physical processes. The examples of band-pass filtered Ne data are shown in Fig. 7. We can observe differences in the distribution of different signal bands over the satellite orbital track.

Figure 7 Example high-level data (selected frequency bands) extracted from residual Ne of Swarm Alpha by band-pass filtering with indicated equator (red dashed) and pole (blue dashed) passes.

The band-pass filtering gives also additional opportunity in spectral analysis. The advantage comes from a better selection and parametrization of window types and sizes. The adjustment of STFT windowing in a narrow frequency band enables a more local and precise view of the spectral content. The spectrograms are therefore worth reprocessing in limited frequency bands, which provides inspection of the spectra with new resolution in time and frequency. The high resolution spectrogram is impossible at high frequencies if we use long windows, which are required for low frequencies analyzed together. The narrow frequency bands presented in Fig. 7 provide a basis for more precise spectrograms, which provide complementary high-level product of DISPEC, together with primary data-based product.

5.2 Ground-based data domain

Ground-based ionospheric observations are referred to non-movable stations collecting measurements over time. Therefore station-based time series have a natural time unit, providing domain for spectral analysis. Therefore spectral characteristics can be analyzed in frequency or wave period units sampled from time unit. The evolutionary PSD analysis of ground-based stationary data will be time-frequency STFT analysis.

5.2.1 Spectral analysis

The signals of ionospheric observations collected at ground-based stations provide time series of static observations, at fixed geodetic locations. Additionally, different stations (e.g. GNSS, Digisonde, DORIS etc.) compose the networks, which are quite homogeneously distributed globally, as they are managed by different IUGG services. Local dense networks are less frequent, and established mainly in the regions requiring

particularly careful monitoring of ionosphere or lithosphere (e.g. very active seismically). Therefore small-scale ionospheric irregularities can be spatially analyzed only over these local dense networks. The global networks can be used in a spatial domain for detection of large-scale ionospheric features, e.g. EIA anomaly or auroral oval. Nevertheless, a very dense time resolution of station-based data in connection with collected long time series provide a very interesting basis for analysis of large-scale and small-scale variations of ionosphere in time domain. This is possible, because we can extract from such time series a frequency domain, which is extended over a really wide frequency band. The time series of ionospheric observations from ground-based stations are often characterized by a long-term trend, as we know at least solar 11-year cycle triggering long-term variation of the ionosphere. Some exceptions, of course, will be found for selected quantities, but generally ground-based data need high-pass filtering, which will be done in exactly same way as for along-track data. The trend for VTEC time series from IGS NICO station generated by low-pass filter with example bound of 60 days (Fig. 8, upper subfigure, red line) is subtracted, which provides the high-pass filtered residuals shown in bottom subfigure of Fig. 8.

Figure 8 Yearly time series of VTEC collected by IGS NICO station (black line) and trend (red line) determined by DFT with maximum wave period of 60 months (upper figure). Residual VTEC after subtraction of 60-month trend (bottom figure).

The high-pass filtered VTEC exhibits apparently noisy nature in Fig. 8, but this illusion comes from high-amplitude strongly periodic signals and compression of long time series along the time axis. The dominating and continuous (which can be stated as strongly periodic) are diurnal and sub-diurnal wave periods, which repeat 365 or more times over quite compressed x-axis in Fig. 8. The spectrogram calculated by STFT with the use of 60-day Tukey window presents these strongest signals well, revealing also interesting longer-wavelength variabilities of VTEC, i.e. wave periods between diurnal and

2-month period (Fig. 9). The sub-diurnal periods are hidden in this spectrogram due to the wide frequency band analyzed together, which consequently imposes large window size in comparison to the frequency of sub-diurnal variabilities. This fact leads to the conclusion on some challenge present in processing of wide frequency band of the signal. Therefore DISPEC assumes band-pass filtering, which on the one hand empowers operating at a narrower signal band, and on the other hand, gives an opportunity to filter out dominating strong diurnal/sub-diurnal signals, which are placed in the middle of frequency band and impede the analysis.

Figure 9 Spectrogram of residual yearly VTEC time series collected by IGS NICO station after subtraction of 60-month trend.

An example ancillary signal, which can be investigated together with station-based ionospheric data can be any quantity determined continuously in time (with minor gaps), and collected in constant time intervals. It is clear that global parameters will have more universal applicability, whereas local quantities describing state of the ionosphere, magnetosphere, lithosphere or other coupled environment must be applied after considering their time-space co-location with selected ground-based data. The example of global parameter is geomagnetic ap60 index, which has hourly time resolution (Yamazaki et al 2022). The ap60 index is produced by Geomagnetic Observatory Niemeck, GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, and is unitless. This geomagnetic index at quiet state of magnetosphere can drop even to zero, which raises a question about an expected value of its statistical distribution. This issue is to be solved in DISPEC project. A preliminary view of wave-like structures at different wave periods of ap60 yearly time series is made after applying of high-pass filter with the same filtering

bound as for VTEC series. The 60-day trend of ap60 index is shown in upper subfigure of Fig. 10 (red) and residuals are given in bottom subfigure of Fig. 10.

Figure 10 Yearly time series of ap60 index (black line) and trend (red line) determined by DFT with maximum wave period of 60 months (upper figure). Residual series of ap60 index after subtraction of 60-month trend (bottom figure).

The ap60 is high-pass filtered and processed with STFT technique using the same 60-day window, as that for VTEC spectrogram. The high-pass filtering at this bound causes that entire signal from lower frequencies is filtered out. Remaining minor spectral leakage effects in Fig. 11 can be eliminated with a better window parameter adjustment. It is an objective of DISPEC to prove that narrow separated frequency bands provide significant benefit in signal analysis, due to the resolution assured by more adequate windowing. Figure 12 presents cross-spectrogram describing evolutionary CSD of two signals and potentially significant resonant signals at selected frequencies. The CSD requires common sampling frequency, and theoretically it has no importance whether the signal of lower resolution is sampled at higher resolution, or reversely. In the presented case, a denser VTEC signal is sampled at hourly time interval of ap60, but reverse process would also theoretically work. The interpolation of sparse signal at higher frequency would simply not provide a higher-frequency signal, if the interpolation method avoided artificial signal generation. The CSD in Fig. 12 reveals a resonant diurnal periodicity, which is obvious and strong in VTEC (Fig. 9), but can be also noticed as weak signal at that frequency in Fig. 11. The other strong resonant signals are available at around two-week and one-month wave periods, and start around September 2020, when solar activity starts to vary more than in relatively quiet first part of year 2000.

Figure 11 Spectrogram of yearly record of ap60 index after subtraction of 60-month trend.

Figure 12 Evolutionary cross-spectrogram of residual VTEC at NICO and ap60.

As it was pointed out in sec. 5.1, the CSD is a relative measure of correlation, and its' estimate can suffer from differences in the amplitude range of different signal frequencies. For statistical assessment, the normalized MSC can be applied. However, the MSC calculation is more demanding in respect of data sample lengths, which makes its use challenging at lower frequencies. A rough, very preliminary calculation of MSC, with intuitively selecting sampling needing further rounds of adjustment in the frame of DISPEC, is shown in Fig. 13. A high MSC at several frequencies may be overestimated due

to too small number of samples or also due to low signal amplitudes in PSD of one or two signals. These issues must be investigated in DISPEC.

Figure 13 Preliminary test of coherence estimation between VTEC at NICO and Hp60. The parameters will be adjusted.

5.2.2 High-level outputs

The spectrogram in Fig. 9, in comparison to spectrogram in Fig. 2, suggests that in case of station-based long time series the signal is much more heterogeneous in frequency, in comparison to along-track signal. Two issues contribute to this property most: a wider frequency band in case of station-based data and higher diversity of physical processes occurred in the ionosphere, magnetosphere and other coupled environments over these wide frequency band. Thus, if we know from Sec. 5.1 that high-level products can be generated by band-pass filters applied to along-track data, we can easily imagine at least a few high-level data products generated from ground-based time series. Figure 14 presents three selected filtered frequency bands of VTEC time series at NICO, which present absolutely different behavior, and can be probably compared with totally different physical processes. The narrow frequency bands presented in Fig. 14 provide a basis for more precise spectrograms, which according to DISPEC assumptions will provide complementary high-level product together with primary data-based product.

Figure 14 Example high-level data (selected frequency bands) extracted from residual VTEC at NICO by band-pass filtering.

5.3 Model-based data domain

Model-based ionospheric data are characterized by very similar processing domain as station-based data, as they are time series. The differences can come from lower spatiotemporal resolution of the models, which is typically degraded during modeling processes (spherical harmonics, tomography, kriging, splines etc.). In order to give an example difference we can compare the series of VTEC determined from station-based RINEX data, and time series of the same interval interpolated from GIM model. The former series can have physical resolution of seconds and make possible the analysis of small disturbances at minute order wave period. The latter time series have typically hourly resolution significantly impeding analysis at wave periods shorter than sub-diurnal. The spatial grid nature of the models facilitates interpolation at arbitrary geolocation, whereas time interval of the models determines Nyquist frequency of sampling in the frequency domain. Therefore the evolutionary PSD analysis of model-based stationary data will be time-frequency STFT analysis, with the frequency limited by the time frequency of gridded maps. Thus, the spectral analysis of model-based time series will be basically very similar to spectral analysis of station-based series. The advantage of the models comes from an easy generation of time series at arbitrary locations over the globe, and potentially smaller number of data gaps in these series, as the models can be based on more than one data type.

6. Summary and conclusions/additional remarks

The proposed scheme and workflow of spectral data analysis and filter-based generation of high-level products are applied to:

- Satellite along-track data (time-space-frequency analysis)
- Station-based (ground-based) time series of the data (time-frequency analysis)
- Time series of stationary data at selected locations generated from the ionosphere models of different type (time-frequency analysis)

The band-pass filtering fills the database of new high-level data products, which are more efficient in the application in correlation analyses with coupled or related phenomena/quantities and also in the modeling processes. The new high-level data products based on spectral filtering selectively represent desired data issues, also those related with ionospheric processes, e.g.

- removal of long-term trends related with long-term processes up to very high frequencies
- removal of high-frequency noise
- selection of residual signal from precisely determined frequency band
- filtering out some mid-frequency impeding signal, like e.g. diurnal or seasonal variations
- signal divided into narrow bands empowering calculation of the spectrograms with increased resolution and representation of more specific (narrower) scope of physical processes